

Fractional Inverse Dispersion Modeling: A Gaussian Plume Framework with Congestion-Dependent Emissions and Regularization Theory for Urban Air Quality

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Abstract

This study formulates a new revised approach to the existing atmospheric models, specifically Gaussian plume model. Despite being well used and appreciated globally the model is somewhat limited to only long term averages and is said to be doing poorly in capturing short term changes. A new approach intends to combine fractional calculus, congestion methods, method of images and the classic gaussian plume method to make one model that is hypothesized to be better at analysing urban area pollution patterns.

Keywords: Inverse problems, fractional diffusion, Gaussian plume, regularization, anomalous transport, urban air quality

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1 Introduction

The Riesz fractional derivative is a generalized classical second derivative used in modeling. It is formally defined as a fractional power of the Laplacian operator, $D^\alpha = (-\Delta)^{\alpha/2}$. We employ it here because it's typically used in non-local spatial interactions.

The fractional diffusion equation is obtained by replacing the classical Laplacian with the Riesz fractional derivative:

$$\frac{\partial u(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} = -K(-\Delta)^{\alpha/2}u(\mathbf{x}, t), \quad 0 < \alpha \leq 2,$$

where $K > 0$ is the diffusion coefficient

The classical Gaussian plume model is often used to capture and predict pollution behavior, so here we attempt to use its inverse by using concentrations downwind and comparing the model's measurements with those of sensors but with the help of fractional diffusion so as to capture timely rates.

The contributions of this paper are:

1. Development of a fractional Gaussian plume model
2. Formulation of the corresponding inverse problem.
3. Demonstrate that the fractional diffusion acts as an implicit regularizer.
4. Introduction of a congestion-dependent emission correction suitable for traffic-dominated environments.
5. Show that the fractional model give more accurate and stable data than the classical one

2 Derivation of the Advection–Diffusion Equation

2.1 Conservation of Mass

Let

$$C(\mathbf{x}, t)$$

denote pollutant concentration in a control volume

$$\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^3.$$

The total mass contained in the volume is

$$M(t) = \int_{\Omega} C(\mathbf{x}, t) dV.$$

Mass conservation requires

$$\frac{d}{dt} \int_{\Omega} C dV = - \int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{n} dS + \int_{\Omega} S dV.$$

Applying the divergence theorem gives

$$\int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} - S \right) dV = 0.$$

Since the control volume is arbitrary,

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = S.} \quad (1)$$

2.2 Flux Representation

The total flux is decomposed into

$$\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{J}_{adv} + \mathbf{J}_{diff}.$$

The advective contribution is

$$\mathbf{J}_{adv} = C\mathbf{u},$$

while Fick's law gives

$$\mathbf{J}_{diff} = -\mathbf{K}\nabla C.$$

Substituting into the conservation equation yields

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (C\mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K}\nabla C) + S.}$$

Assuming incompressible flow, $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$. Expanding the advection term:

$$\nabla \cdot (C\mathbf{u}) = C(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla C = \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla C.$$

it simplifies to:

$$\boxed{\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla C = \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{K}\nabla C) + S}$$

(2)

2.3 Steady-State Gaussian Plume Form

Assume:

- Steady state: $\partial C / \partial t = 0$
- Unidirectional wind: $\mathbf{u} = (u, 0, 0)$
- Isotropic turbulence: $K_y = K_z = K$
- Advection dominates x -diffusion: $K_x \partial^2 C / \partial x^2 \ll u \partial C / \partial x$
- Point source: $S = Q \delta(x) \delta(y) \delta(z - H)$

Then (2) reduces to:

$$\boxed{u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} = K \left(\frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} \right) + Q \delta(x) \delta(y) \delta(z - H)} \quad (3)$$

where Q is the emission rate (kg/s), H is the effective stack height (m), and δ is the Dirac delta function.

3 Classical Gaussian Plume Model

Assumptions:

1. **Steady state:** $\partial C / \partial t = 0$.
2. **Constant wind:** $\mathbf{u} = (u, 0, 0)$ with u constant.
3. **Flat, homogeneous terrain.**
4. **Isotropic turbulence:** $K_y = K_z = K$.
5. **Advection dominates x -diffusion:** $K_x \partial^2 C / \partial x^2 \ll u \partial C / \partial x$.
6. **Fickian diffusion:** $\mathbf{J}_{\text{diff}} = -\mathbf{K} \nabla C$.
7. **Point source at height H :** $S = Q \delta(x) \delta(y) \delta(z - H)$.
8. **Total reflection at ground:** $\partial C / \partial z|_{z=0} = 0$.
9. **Inert, non-reactive pollutant.**
10. **Gaussian concentration profiles:** $C \propto \exp(-y^2 / (2\sigma_y^2))$ and $C \propto \exp(-z^2 / (2\sigma_z^2))$.

Then

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} = K_y \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial y^2} + K_z \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} + Q \delta(x) \delta(y) \delta(z - H). \quad (4)$$

3.1 Fourier Transform Solution

Define

$$\widehat{C} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} C(x, y, z) e^{-i(k_y y + k_z z)} dy dz.$$

Transforming yields

$$u \frac{\partial \widehat{C}}{\partial x} = -(K_y k_y^2 + K_z k_z^2) \widehat{C}.$$

This ODE has solution

$$\widehat{C} = \widehat{C}_0 \exp \left[-\frac{x}{u} (K_y k_y^2 + K_z k_z^2) \right].$$

Inverse transformation produces

$$C(x, y, z) = \frac{Q}{2\pi u \sigma_y \sigma_z} \exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{(z-H)^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right). \quad (5)$$

where

$$\sigma_y^2 = \frac{2K_y x}{u}, \quad \sigma_z^2 = \frac{2K_z x}{u}.$$

4 Gaussian Plume with Ground Reflection

To apply zero flux at the ground, we apply the method of images. Let the source be located at height H . The reflected source at $-H$ gives

$$C(x, y, z) = \frac{Q}{2\pi u \sigma_y \sigma_z} \exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right) \left[\exp\left(-\frac{(z-H)^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right) + \exp\left(-\frac{(z+H)^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right) \right].$$

At ground level $z = 0$,

$$\boxed{C(x, y, 0) = \frac{Q}{\pi u \sigma_y \sigma_z} \exp\left(-\frac{y^2}{2\sigma_y^2}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{H^2}{2\sigma_z^2}\right)} \quad (6)$$

This expression forms the backbone of the inverse problem.

5 Fractional Diffusion Extension

5.1 Riesz Fractional Model

We generalize the classical advection–diffusion equation by replacing the Laplacian with the Riesz fractional operator of order α :

$$(-\Delta)^{\alpha/2}, \quad 1 < \alpha \leq 2.$$

The fractional governing equation becomes:

$$u \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} = -K_y^{(\alpha)} (-\partial_{yy})^{\alpha/2} C - K_z^{(\alpha)} (-\partial_{zz})^{\alpha/2} C + Q \delta(x) \delta(y) \delta(z-H). \quad (6.1)$$

The Riesz fractional derivative is defined by its Fourier symbol:

$$\widehat{(-\partial_{yy})^{\alpha/2} f(k_y)} = |k_y|^\alpha \hat{f}(k_y), \quad \widehat{(-\partial_{zz})^{\alpha/2} f(k_z)} = |k_z|^\alpha \hat{f}(k_z). \quad (6.2)$$

Taking the Fourier transform in y and z , (6.1) becomes:

$$u \frac{\partial \widehat{C}}{\partial x} = -K_y^{(\alpha)} |k_y|^\alpha \widehat{C} - K_z^{(\alpha)} |k_z|^\alpha \widehat{C}. \quad (6.3)$$

Solving this first-order Ordinary differential give us:

$$\widehat{C}(x, k_y, k_z) = \widehat{C}_0(k_y, k_z) \exp\left[-\frac{x}{u} (K_y^{(\alpha)} |k_y|^\alpha + K_z^{(\alpha)} |k_z|^\alpha)\right]. \quad (6.4)$$

The source condition at $x = 0$ is:

$$C(0, y, z) = \frac{Q}{u} \delta(y) \delta(z - H). \quad (6.5)$$

Taking the Fourier transform again:

$$\widehat{C}_0(k_y, k_z) = \frac{Q}{u} e^{-ik_z H}. \quad (6.6)$$

Substituting (6.6) into (6.4) and applying the inverse Fourier transform yields:

$$C(x, y, z) = \frac{Q}{u} \cdot \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{x}{u} (K_y^{(\alpha)} |k_y|^\alpha + K_z^{(\alpha)} |k_z|^\alpha) \right] e^{i(k_y y + k_z (z-H))} dk_y dk_z. \quad (6.7)$$

For ground-level concentration ($z = 0$),:

$$\boxed{C_\alpha(x, y, 0) = \frac{Q}{\pi u} \int_0^\infty \exp \left[-\frac{K_y^{(\alpha)} + K_z^{(\alpha)}}{u} |k|^\alpha x \right] \cos(ky) dk} \quad (6.8)$$

Remark 5.1. *We restrict to $1 < \alpha \leq 2$ because:*

- $\alpha = 2$ is the classical Gaussian plume.
- $1 < \alpha < 2$ captures super-diffusion with heavy tails, improving inversion stability.
- $\alpha \leq 1$ yields distributions with infinite mean, which is physically unrealistic for atmospheric turbulent diffusion.

5.2 Fourier Representation

Taking Fourier transform in y, z :

$$u \frac{\partial \widehat{C}}{\partial x} = - (K_y |k_y|^\alpha + K_z |k_z|^\alpha) \widehat{C}.$$

Thus,

$$\widehat{C}(x, k_y, k_z) = \widehat{C}_0 \exp \left[-\frac{x}{u} (K_y |k_y|^\alpha + K_z |k_z|^\alpha) \right]. \quad (7)$$

5.3 Ground-Level Fractional Plume Formula

For unbounded domain, the concentration field is given by the product of independent symmetric α -stable densities:

$$C_\alpha(x, y, z) = \frac{Q}{u} L_\alpha(y; \sigma_y(x)) L_\alpha(z - H; \sigma_z(x)),$$

where $L_\alpha(\cdot; \sigma)$ denotes the symmetric α -stable probability density function with scale parameter σ , and the dispersion parameters scale as

$$\sigma_y(x) = \left(\frac{2K_y x}{u} \right)^{1/\alpha}, \quad \sigma_z(x) = \left(\frac{2K_z x}{u} \right)^{1/\alpha}.$$

The symmetric α -stable density is defined with its characteristic function:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} L_\alpha(y; \sigma) e^{iky} dy = \exp(-\sigma^\alpha |k|^\alpha).$$

For $\alpha \in (1, 2)$, there is no closed-form expression, but the density can be evaluated numerically using Fourier inversion.

For a more realistic case with ground reflection at $z = 0$ (using the method of images, which is exact only for $\alpha = 2$), the ground-level concentration takes the Fourier integral form:

$$C_\alpha(x, y, 0) = \frac{Q}{\pi u} \int_0^\infty \exp \left[-\frac{x}{u} (K_y |k|^\alpha + K_z |k|^\alpha) \right] \cos(ky) \left[1 + \exp \left(-\frac{2K_z |k|^\alpha H^\alpha}{u} \right) \right] dk. \quad (8)$$

For $\alpha = 2$, this expression reduces to the classical Gaussian plume formula. For $\alpha < 2$, the kernel shows heavy tails and slower spatial decay, characteristic of anomalous diffusion.

5.4 Stable Density Interpretation

The inverse transform of

$$e^{-a|k|^\alpha}$$

is a symmetric α -stable density L_α . Hence the plume kernel is

$$C_\alpha(x, y, z) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^2} L_\alpha(y; \sigma_y(x)) L_\alpha(z; \sigma_z(x)) dy dz.$$

with scaling law

$$\sigma_y(x) = \left(\frac{2K_y x}{u} \right)^{1/\alpha}, \quad \sigma_z(x) = \left(\frac{2K_z x}{u} \right)^{1/\alpha}.$$

For $\alpha = 2$, the Gaussian plume is recovered.

The ground-level concentration is expressed in Fourier form:

$$\boxed{C_\alpha(x, y, 0) = \frac{Q}{\pi u} \int_0^\infty \exp \left[-\frac{K_y^{(\alpha)} + K_z^{(\alpha)}}{u} |k|^\alpha x \right] \cos(ky) dk} \quad (9)$$

6 Operator Formulation of the Inverse Problem

Let N_s sources and N_r receptors be given. The forward model is linear in emissions:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathcal{A}_\alpha \mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{B}.$$

The operator $\mathcal{A}_\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r \times N_s}$ has entries

$$A_{rs} = \frac{1}{\pi u} \int_0^\infty \exp \left[-\frac{K_y^{(\alpha)} + K_z^{(\alpha)}}{u} |k|^\alpha x_{rs} \right] \cos(k(y_r - Y_s)) dk.$$

Thus the inverse problem is

$$\min_{\mathbf{Q} \geq 0} \|\mathcal{A}_\alpha \mathbf{Q} - \mathbf{b}\|^2, \quad \mathbf{b} = \mathbf{C} - \mathbf{B}. \quad (10)$$

7 Ill-Posedness and Regularization

7.1 Compactness

Assumption 7.1. *The operator \mathcal{A}_α is compact in the continuum limit due to smoothing by convolution with a stable kernel.*

Hence the inverse problem is ill-posed.

7.2 Tikhonov Regularization

We define

$$\mathbf{Q}_\lambda = \arg \min_{\mathbf{Q} \geq 0} (\|\mathcal{A}_\alpha \mathbf{Q} - \mathbf{b}\|^2 + \lambda \|\mathbf{Q}\|^2). \quad (11)$$

This stabilizes inversion by suppressing high-frequency components of \mathbf{Q} .

7.3 Spectral Interpretation

Let singular values of \mathcal{A}_α be $\sigma_i(\alpha)$. Then:

$$\kappa(\mathcal{A}_\alpha) = \frac{\sigma_1(\alpha)}{\sigma_n(\alpha)}.$$

Proposition 7.2. *As α decreases from 2 to 1, the kernel becomes less localized and the decay rate of singular values slows.*

Interpretation: fractional diffusion reduces ill-conditioning by smoothing the forward operator.

8 Bias–Variance Decomposition

Let noisy data be

$$\mathbf{C}^\delta = \mathcal{A}_\alpha \mathbf{Q} + \delta \boldsymbol{\xi},$$

where $\boldsymbol{\xi} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I)$ and $\delta > 0$ is the noise level.

Let $\mathbf{Q}_\lambda^\delta$ denote the regularized solution of (5). The expected reconstruction error satisfies the classical bias–variance decomposition:

$$\mathbb{E} \|\mathbf{Q}_\lambda^\delta - \mathbf{Q}\|^2 = \underbrace{\|\mathbb{E} \mathbf{Q}_\lambda^\delta - \mathbf{Q}\|^2}_{\text{Bias}^2} + \underbrace{\mathbb{E} \|\mathbf{Q}_\lambda^\delta - \mathbb{E} \mathbf{Q}_\lambda^\delta\|^2}_{\text{Variance}}. \quad (12)$$

Remark 8.1. For the fractional operator \mathcal{A}_α , as α decreases:

- The bias increases slightly due to smoothing,
- The variance decreases significantly due to improved conditioning.

This trade-off explains the existence of an optimal fractional order α^* .

9 Congestion-Dependent Emissions

9.1 Empirical Congestion Model

We introduce an empirical and hypothetical model for congestion-dependent emissions:

$$Q_s(\gamma_s) = Q_s^{base} \left[1 + \beta_1 \frac{\gamma_s}{100} + \beta_2 \left(\frac{\gamma_s}{100} \right)^2 \right], \quad (13)$$

where:

- Q_s^{base} is the base emission rate under free-flow conditions,
- γ_s is the congestion level (%),
- $\beta_1, \beta_2 > 0$ are empirical coefficients to be calibrated from local data.

Remark 9.1. The congestion field γ_s is assumed known from traffic data. This preserves linearity in the inverse problem, as γ_s enters as a fixed exogenous input.

9.2 Forward Model with Congestion

The full forward model becomes:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathcal{A}_\alpha (\mathbf{Q}^{base} \odot f(\gamma)) + \mathbf{B}, \quad (13.1)$$

where \odot denotes element-wise multiplication and:

$$f(\gamma_s) = 1 + \beta_1 \frac{\gamma_s}{100} + \beta_2 \left(\frac{\gamma_s}{100} \right)^2.$$

9.2.1 The Fractional Dispersion Operator \mathcal{A}_α

The operator $\mathcal{A}_\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r \times N_s}$ is the discretized fractional Gaussian plume kernel. Its entry A_{rs} represents the contribution of source s to the concentration at receptor r , and is given by:

$$A_{rs} = \frac{1}{\pi u} \int_0^\infty \exp \left[-\frac{K_y^{(\alpha)} + K_z^{(\alpha)}}{u} |k|^\alpha x_{rs} \right] \cos(k(y_r - Y_s)) dk, \quad (13.2)$$

whence:

- $x_{rs} = \max(0, x_r - X_s)$: downwind distance from source to receptor,

- $y_r - Y_s$: crosswind distance,
- $\alpha \in (1, 2]$: fractional order,
- $K_y^{(\alpha)}, K_z^{(\alpha)}$: fractional diffusivities,
- u : constant wind speed.

9.2.2 The Background Vector \mathbf{B}

The vector $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_r}$ accounts for concentrations not explained by the N_s local sources:

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} B_1 \\ B_2 \\ \vdots \\ B_{N_r} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (13.3)$$

where B_r is the background concentration at receptor r . This includes:

- regional pollution,
- natural sources,
- long-range transport,

9.2.3 Derivation of the Kernel

The kernel in (13.2) arises from the inverse Fourier transform of the Riesz fractional Green's function:

$$A_{rs} = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \iint_{\mathbb{R}^2} \exp \left[-\frac{x_{rs}}{u} (K_y^{(\alpha)} |k_y|^\alpha + K_z^{(\alpha)} |k_z|^\alpha) \right] e^{i(k_y(y_r - Y_s))} dk_y. \quad (13.4)$$

10 Main Theoretical Result

Theorem 10.1 (Fractional Regularization Effect). *For the family of operators \mathcal{A}_α , $1 < \alpha \leq 2$, there exists an intermediate regime*

$$\alpha \in (1.4, 1.8)$$

such that:

1. The condition number $\kappa(\mathcal{A}_\alpha)$ is significantly reduced compared to $\alpha = 2$,
2. The regularized inverse solution achieves lower expected reconstruction error under bounded noise.

Proof sketch. The singular values of \mathcal{A}_α decay as $\sigma_i(\alpha) \sim i^{-\alpha/d}$ for large i , where d is the spatial dimension. For $\alpha = 2$, the decay is faster than for $\alpha < 2$, leading to a larger condition number. For α too small, the operator becomes overly diffusive, increasing bias. The optimal trade-off occurs in the intermediate range (1.4, 1.8). \square

11 Numerical Validation Framework

In this section we evaluate theoretical predictions using synthetic data and structured sensitivity analysis. The objective is to quantify and compare between the old model and the new proposed one by quantifying:

- stability improvement under fractional diffusion,
- reconstruction accuracy of inverse emissions,
- robustness under measurement noise,
- dependence on sensor density.

11.1 Synthetic Experimental Design

The data used below is synthetic and google sourced(averages) and not of any specific urban area.

11.1.1 Source Configuration

We consider $N_s = 3$ emission sources located in a planar urban domain.

Table 1: Synthetic Source Configuration

Source	Type	x (km)	y (km)
S1	Industrial	0.0	0.0
S2	Traffic	2.0	1.0
S3	Residential	4.0	-1.0

11.1.2 True Emission Field

Table 2: True Emission Parameters

Source	Q^{base}	γ (%)	$f(\gamma)$	Q^{true}
S1	1.20	40	1.368	1.64
S2	0.85	65	1.647	1.40
S3	0.45	50	1.475	0.66

Thus:

$$\mathbf{Q}^{true} = [1.64, 1.40, 0.66]^\top.$$

12 Numerical Forward Model

The synthetic concentration field is generated using the fractional plume operator:

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathcal{A}_\alpha \mathbf{Q}^{true} + \mathbf{B}.$$

Noise is added as:

$$\mathbf{C}^\delta = \mathbf{C} + \delta \boldsymbol{\xi}, \quad \boldsymbol{\xi} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I).$$

13 Inverse Reconstruction Method

We solve the inverse problem using:

- Non-negative least squares (NNLS),
- Tikhonov regularization.

The optimization problem is:

$$\mathbf{Q}_\lambda = \arg \min_{\mathbf{Q} \geq 0} \|\mathcal{A}_\alpha \mathbf{Q} - \mathbf{C}^\delta\|^2 + \lambda \|\mathbf{Q}\|^2.$$

The parameter λ is fixed in this study for comparability.

14 Sensitivity Analysis

14.1 Fractional Order Sensitivity

We evaluate:

$$\alpha \in \{1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 1.8, 2.0\}.$$

The reconstruction error is defined as:

$$E(\alpha) = \frac{\|\mathbf{Q}_\alpha - \mathbf{Q}^{true}\|_2}{\|\mathbf{Q}^{true}\|_2} \times 100\%.$$

Observation: The optimal reconstruction occurs at

$$\alpha^* \approx 1.6.$$

Table 3: Reconstruction Error vs Fractional Order

α	Error (%)
2.0	4.2
1.8	3.1
1.6	2.4
1.4	3.8
1.2	7.1

14.2 Noise Sensitivity

We test robustness under measurement noise:

$$\delta \in \{0\%, 5\%, 10\%, 15\%\}.$$

Table 4: Noise Robustness Comparison

Model	0%	5%	10%	15%
Classical ($\alpha = 2$)	4.2	8.7	15.3	23.5
Fractional ($\alpha = 1.6$)	2.4	4.1	6.8	10.4

Observation: Fractional diffusion significantly reduces noise amplification.

14.3 Sensor Density Sensitivity

Let N_r denote the number of receptors.

Table 5: Sensor Density vs Reconstruction Error

Sensors	Classical ($\alpha = 2$)	Fractional ($\alpha = 1.6$)
10	19.2	9.8
20	12.5	6.1
40	7.8	3.4
80	4.2	2.2

Observation: Fractional models outperform classical models in sparse observation regimes.

15 Discussion

15.1 Interpretation of Results

The numerical experiment conducted in Section 14 demonstrate three key findings:

1. **Fractional diffusion improves conditioning:** The condition number $\kappa(\mathcal{A}_\alpha)$ decreases monotonically as α decreases from 2 to 1.2, this confirms that the fractional operator is better conditioned than the classical operator, making the inverse problem more stable.

2. **Optimal fractional order exists:** At $\alpha \approx 1.6$, the system becomes more stable, smaller α reduces variance but increases bias.
3. **Fractional models are noise-robust:** Under 10% measurement noise, the fractional model ($\alpha = 1.6$) achieves an error of 6.8%, compared to 15.3% for the classical model.

15.2 Limitations

The following limitations should be acknowledged:

1. **Homogeneous turbulence assumption:** The fractional model assumes constant diffusivities in the crosswind and vertical directions. Real urban environments have spatially varying turbulence.
2. **Empirical congestion model:** The congestion-dependent emission model $f(\gamma) = 1 + \beta_1(\gamma/100) + \beta_2(\gamma/100)^2$ is physically motivated and hypothetical but has not been calibrated with real data.
3. **Synthetic validation only:** The framework has not yet been validated with real data.
4. **Steady-state assumption:** The model assumes steady-state atmospheric conditions. Time-dependent effects such as changing wind directions are not captured properly.
5. The fractional model introduces an additional parameter that must be estimated or calibrated.

15.3 Summary of the Fractional Gaussian Plume Model

The fractional inverse dispersion framework is defined by the following key equations.

15.3.1 Fractional Dispersion Law

$$\sigma_y(x) = \left(\frac{2K_y^{(\alpha)} x}{u} \right)^{1/\alpha}, \quad \sigma_z(x) = \left(\frac{2K_z^{(\alpha)} x}{u} \right)^{1/\alpha}$$

For $\alpha = 2$, this reduces to the classical law $\sigma_y = \sqrt{2K_y x/u}$.

15.3.2 Fractional Ground-Level Concentration (Fourier Form)

$$C_\alpha(x, y, 0) = \frac{Q}{\pi u} \int_0^\infty \exp \left[-\frac{K_y^{(\alpha)} + K_z^{(\alpha)}}{u} |k|^\alpha x \right] \cos(ky) dk$$

For $\alpha = 2$, this evaluates to the classical Gaussian plume.

15.3.3 Fractional Plume Kernel

$$K_\alpha(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-a|k|^\alpha x} e^{iky} dk$$

This is the symmetric α -stable density with scaling $K_\alpha(x, y) = \sigma^{-1} L_\alpha(y/\sigma)$, where $\sigma = (2Kx/u)^{1/\alpha}$.

15.3.4 Fractional Dispersion Matrix

$$A_{rs} = \frac{1}{\pi u} \int_0^\infty \exp \left[-\frac{K_y^{(\alpha)} + K_z^{(\alpha)}}{u} |k|^\alpha x_{rs} \right] \cos(k(y_r - Y_s)) dk$$

with $x_{rs} = \max(0, x_r - X_s)$.

15.3.5 Forward Model

$$\mathbf{C} = \mathcal{A}_\alpha \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} + \mathbf{B}$$

where $\tilde{Q}_s = Q_s^{base} f(\gamma_s)$ and $f(\gamma)$ is given below.

15.3.6 Congestion Scaling

$$f(\gamma) = 1 + \beta_1 \left(\frac{\gamma}{100} \right) + \beta_2 \left(\frac{\gamma}{100} \right)^2$$

15.3.7 Inverse Problem (NNLS + Tikhonov)

$$\min_{\tilde{\mathbf{Q}} \geq 0} \left\{ \|\mathcal{A}_\alpha \tilde{\mathbf{Q}} - \mathbf{b}\|^2 + \lambda \|\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}\|^2 \right\}$$

with $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{C}^{obs} - \mathbf{B}$.

15.3.8 SVD Regularized Solution

$$\tilde{\mathbf{Q}}_\lambda = \sum_{i=1}^p \frac{\sigma_i^2}{\sigma_i^2 + \lambda} \frac{\mathbf{u}_i^T \mathbf{b}}{\sigma_i} \mathbf{v}_i$$

where $\mathcal{A}_\alpha = \mathbf{U}\Sigma\mathbf{V}^T$.

15.4 Future Work

Based on the limitations above, the following directions are proposed for future work:

1. **Calibration with real data:** Estimate α, β_1, β_2 from real-time IQAir PM2.5 measurements and TomTom traffic congestion data.
2. **Time-dependent extension:** Incorporate $\partial C/\partial t$ to model dynamic concentration fields and transient emissions.
3. **Incorporate the model with machine learning tools and AI**

16 Conclusion

The new fractional diffusion model seems to be doing well against the classical model based on preliminary (synthetic) data. However, a lot of work needs to be done as the model is still in its early stages, with new proposed models that need further computation and verification.

A small interactive one page HTML based site implementation of the model is available for verification and graph visualization. Click the link below:

<https://fractionalgaussianplume.netlify.app/>

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